

TOURISM, THE POTENTIALITY OF SURKHANDARYA. TODAY AND THE FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the distinctive features of tourism as a fast-growing industry in the world. It shows Surkhandarya region which is in the Republic of Uzbekistan as an attractive place of tourism and its importance in the development of the country's tourism industry system. The paper also considers the state and prospects of development of this sphere of activity in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Currently, tourism is one of the fastest growing sectors of the economy in many parts of the world. Tourism has become the third largest sector of the world economy. The United Nations General Assembly has declared 2017 the International year of sustainable tourism. It should be emphasized that tourism is gaining popularity - according to forecasts of the world tourism organization, Tourism towards the historical places is among the five main strategic directions for tourism development, and estimated the share of this tourism in the total volume of the global tourism industry in recent years has reached the growth and rate is 2-3 times higher than the respective rates of growth of the entire tourism industry.

Based on these data, it is possible to draw conclusions about the importance of international tourism and the promotion of

inter-ethnic cooperation. This has led to the fact that the countries have fully begun to learn about each other's rich, cultural and historical heritage.

Uzbekistan is planning on building 20 hotels, 60 guesthouses, 4 recreation centers and 6 handicraft centers in the Surkhandarya region in the next 2 years, as well as starting direct flights from Japan, South Korea, India, China, and Turkey.

During the recent videoconference, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev specifically emphasized on creating new jobs, improving service quality in the tourism field, organizing trips to ancient cities and tourist attractions.

During the pandemic hardest hit was the tourism sector, not only in Uzbekistan but worldwide. Since the start of implementing quarantine measures to avoid further

COVID-19 spread, the President of Uzbekistan has been paying special attention to supporting the tourism industry in the country and its related sectors.

Particularly, significantly effective measures on the gradual recovery of the industry have been identified by the Decree of the President dated 28 May 2020 "On urgent measures on supporting the tourism industry to reduce the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic".

The videoconference discussions included the perspectives of creating new internal travel routes in Uzbekistan, increasing the number of resorts, expanding the health & wellness tourism in the country.

Surkhandarya Region has great touristic potential, being an oasis with ancient history, culture, and natural heritage.

Under the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated 27 May 2020 on "Additional measures on effective use and development of the travel potential of Surkhandarya region", the growth of tourist infrastructure of the region will radically change during 2020-2021.

In the framework of the regional investment program, Uzbekistan is planning on building 20 hotels that would provide more than 1.100 new accommodation units, 4 recreation centers for a total number of 170 beds, and 60 guesthouses with 487 accommodation units overall. 6 handicraft centers will open around the main tourist attractions as well as service points.

Additionally, launching direct international flights from Japan, South Korea, India, China, and Turkey to the international airport of Termez city, as well as organizing

internal flights to Samarkand, Bukhara and Fergana cities are planned as a part of the plan.

Negotiations also focused on improving the roads in the region and creating entertainment centers for tourists, such as shopping malls, water-parks, opening new tourist zones in the areas of Surkhandarya that are rich in unique stunning landscapes.

Improving health and recreation tourism is also a part of the project "Golden Triangle". Taken measures include preparing and training well-qualified specialists in the field, as well as creating new jobs in the travel industry in the region.

The President also mentioned that travel opportunities of the ancient cities of Uzbekistan are not being used to their full potential and even many local people have not seen them so far. Due to the mentioned recommendations of the President, more focus would be made on the organization of interesting trips to historical, cultural, archeological, and pilgrimage areas of the Surkhandarya region, where the effects of the pandemic are mitigating, allowing to be safe for tourists.

Surkhandarya region, with its favorable geographical location and natural conditions, has long attracted people, and the history of this country is not only the history of a country or a people, but also an integral part of the history of the peoples of the world. The passage of the Great Silk Road through this country was the basis for the formation of different cultures in different periods and served as a ground for the crossroads of cultures.

In 2001, Boysun was recognized by UNESCO as a "Masterpiece of Oral and Intangible Cultural Heritage" along with its unique cultural traditions, national costumes, folklore, and thirsty tones.

The traditional annual festival of open folklore "Boysun Bahori" has laid a solid foundation for Surkhandarya region to confidently enter the world tourism market. Surkhandarya region has more than 561 monuments of cultural heritage, covering the period from the Paleolithic to the XX century. Of these, 444 are archeological, 36 are architectural and sacred sites, 39 are monumental and art monuments, and 42 are landmarks. These unique tourist resources are mainly located in the Eski Termez and Sherabad regions, and such monuments are also common in other districts of the region. In addition, at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 5.5 hectares of land were allocated in Termez to immortalize the memory of the late Japanese scientist Kato Kyudzo. Work has been done.

The total area in the province is 24,554 ha. Interest in the nature of the Surkhandarya State Reserve is growing not only among the population of Uzbekistan, but also abroad. The reserve is rich in plant species, with more than 600 species of plants found in the area. More than 20 plant species are rare and protected and included in the Red Book. These include Tubergen tulips, Surkhan tulips, anzur onions, snake onions, red earth astragalus, Boysun astragalus and other plants. In particular, international conservation organizations, in particular the UN TD and the GEF, are focusing on the conservation and reproduction of biodiversity on Mount Kohitang, and are planning to implement international

projects in this regard. The Uzbektelemfilm film studio has made a TV film "In the Footsteps of a Morkhor" about a rare and endangered animal species - a stork or a goat with twisted horns, which has been repeatedly shown on national television.

There is also a gorge "Zarautsoy" on the territory of the "Surkhan State Reserve", which depicts hunting scenes on the rocks of the Mesolithic people. These rock paintings depict the hunting scenes of ancient people with other paintings, which are 9-10 thousand years old and are famous for the fact that there are few such rock paintings on earth. The protection of the monument is satisfactory, and there are all the conditions for it to remain one of the main routes in the development of international ecotourism.

Also, in accordance with the instructions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 3, 2018 No 324 on the establishment of small tourist zones-mountain clusters in Sherabad, Boysun, Sariosiya districts of the region in 2019-2020, the Turkish company IDEALIST established Boysun small tourism zone. A master plan was developed. Accordingly, cultural, medical and nature tourism centers reflecting traditional rural life will be created in the area from Omonkhona village of Boysun district to Zovboshi mountainous area. In particular, a large cultural center, workshops of applied arts and crafts, a lawn complex, glass porches, parking and other service facilities will be built in the cultural tourism center, while a hotel, shops, a medical facility, a villa and eco-parks will be built in the nature tourism center. It is planned to build a mountain road station, special areas, a mosque and hotels in the medical tourism center.

In 2021, the implementation of 70 projects to further develop the existing tourism infrastructure and build new ones to develop the tourism potential of the region, in particular:

- 3 objects of ecological and exotic tourism, ie small tourist zones - mountain clusters;
- 40 objects of gastronomic tourism;
- 101 out of 76 tourist routes;
- 45 subjects of 38 tour operators;
- 15 out of 22 tourist vehicles;
- 3 operating guides to 10;
- Increasing the number of information centers from 3 to 5;
- Increasing the number of Wi-Fi zones from 30 to 70;
- It is planned to increase the number of available accommodation facilities to 3,000 by increasing

the number of existing 156 accommodation facilities, ie 56 hotels and 100 family guest houses, to 220.

In addition, it is planned to hold 10 regular local and 5 international events, participate in 5 foreign fairs, and launch domestic and foreign flights.

As a result, by the end of 2021 it is planned to visit more than 100,000 tourists, including 80,000 local and 20,000 foreign tourists, and provide them with hotel services worth 4 billion soums, which is 100% more than last year.

In addition, under the leadership of the State Committee for Tourism Development, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of

Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city khokimiyats and ministries, committees, central banks and commercial banks and major organizations to eliminate more than 1 million. There are clear weekly and monthly plans for domestic tourists to travel to the region.

The role of highways in the internal and external transport links of the region is incomparable. Therefore, in order to create additional conveniences for residents and tourists of the region, there are regular road transport from Termez, Denau, Sherabad to several foreign countries and different parts of the country. In addition, the existence of the Termez-Tashkent railway, Tashguzor-Baysun-Kumkurgan railway and Hayraton railway bridges over the Amudarya River creates a sharp increase in the volume of trade in raw materials and goods, passenger traffic, not only in the region but also throughout the country and neighboring countries.

Modern aircrafts fly from Termez International Airport to the capital Tashkent, as well as to Samarkand, Namangan, Bukhara, Andijan, and abroad to Moscow and Ashgabat. The region has the only river port in the country, Termez.

This, in turn, will contribute to the development of industry, services, agriculture and tourism in Termez and other districts.

The climate and geography of Surkhandarya made it possible to preserve historical monuments, ruins of ancient cities, and untouched natural attractions almost in their original form. Surkhandarya has become an interesting tourist route, where you can see atypical architecture for Uzbekistan, colorful buildings of antiquity,

as well as get acquainted with the unique, original culture characteristic of this region. It is known that Alexander the Great, Genghis Khan, Ibn Battuta, Rui Gonzales de Clavijo passed through Surkhandarya. Since ancient times, Surkhandarya connected the

ancient cities of Sogdiana with Bactria and India. This place has always attracted travelers, explorers and adventurers. There are the most important sights of Surkhandarya region that each traveller must see.

1. Kirk-kiz Fortress

Kyrk-kiz fortress is an architectural monument located in the Termez district and built in the IX-X centuries. Currently, the monument is preserved in ruins, which convey the former greatness of the ancient structure, even after a Millennium. Researchers put forward various

hypotheses as to what function this structure performed in the past. Perhaps it was a country aristocratic palace, a women's madrasah, a khanaka, or a caravanserai. But most of all, historians agree on the version that this structure served as a defensive fortress of old Termez.

2. Khanaka Kokildor-ota

Khanaka Kokildor-ota is located in Termez and was built in the middle of the XI century. This building is a Holy monastery that has become especially revered in the Muslim world. Khanaka is notable for its unusual

layout and architecture. Researchers believe that the building was rebuilt in the XV century: a majestic portal was completed to the front open facade.

3. The Complex of Sultan Saodat

Sultan Saodat – mausoleum complex with tombs of the Termez seyids. In the IX century, the Termez Seyid dynasty was formed, which made a great contribution to the development of the state. Many residents of this region associate their origin with an ancient dynasty. The main complex of mausoleums was built side by side in the XII century, and the rest – in the XV and XVII centuries. They are located on both sides of a long courtyard and consist of four halls with a roof and a dome.

4. Mausoleum of Sayid Waqqas

The current name of Said Waqqas is Ahmab Ibn Abu Sayid Waqqas Termizi. Exact information about the years of life of this scientist and his creative activity has not been preserved. He was buried near the village of bug, where Imam al-Hakim at-Termizi lived. It is believed that Sayid Waqqas, like Imam Termizi, came from the house of Sayid. According to scientists, the mausoleum of Abdullah Sayid Waqqas at-Termizi lived much earlier.

5. The complex of Hakim at-Termizi

The al-Hakim at-Termizi complex is an architectural monument and a sacred place of worship for Muslims. It is located on the outskirts of old Termez. In the mausoleum is buried the outstanding Islamic figure Abu Abdulloh Ibn Hasan Ibn Bashir al-Hakimi at-Termizi, who was also called by the people

respectfully Termez-ota, which means "Father of Termez". At-Termezi complex has several other interesting attractions: chillahona – ancient cave structures of the V-X centuries AD, the ruins of the ancient settlement of Tarmita (Old Termez) and the Museum of the city of Termez.

6. Buddhist temple Fayaz-Tepa

The Fayaztepa temple complex, dating from the first century BC to the 3rd century AD, is located on the territory of old Termez, between the Amu Darya river and the ancient caravan route. Once there were three large buildings: a temple, a monastery, and a courtyard with utility rooms. The complex impresses to this day with its grandeur and unusual layout.

7. Karatepa Buddhist temple complex

Karatepa is a complex of Buddhist temples located in the north-eastern part of old Termez. The monument is built on 3 natural ridges. The total area reached more than 8 hectares. The first Buddhist temples in Karatepa began to appear at the beginning of the 1st century. The temple complex flourished in the II-III centuries AD.

8. Kampyrtepa Fortress

Kampyr – tepa is once existed an ancient city, located 30 km away from the city of Termez, on the right coast of the Amu Darya. In 2018, scientists and archaeologists proved that this was once the residence of Alexander the Great - ancient Alexandria on

the Ox (other name of the Amu Darya). During the archaeological excavations, cultural layers were discovered and valuable items were found that relate to the period when the great commander came here.

9. Khodjaikon salt cave

Khodjaikon salt cave is located in the Sherabad district, and for several years it provides services of sanatorium-resort treatment. One type of service is a type of healing treatment in a salt cave called speleotherapy. The Khodjaikon salt cave was opened in 1989. Staying in such a cave is very useful for patients with asthma, respiratory diseases, chronic bronchitis, complications of pneumonia, as well as skin

diseases and reduced immunity. The advantage of this salt cave over other caves of this type is that the climate is dry and it is located at an altitude of 1200 meters above sea level. Khodjaikon salt cave has a length of 155 meters, inside it there are 3 treatment rooms, which differ from each other in temperature, humidity, pressure and trace elements.

10. Rock paintings Zarautsay

Zarautsay petroglyphs – ancient rock carvings, located in the south-west of Gissar range, on the Eastern slopes of the mountains Kugitang of Sherabad district, in the gorge of Zarautsay. More than 200

images of red angob were found in 1912. The figures Zarautsay depict people hunting with dogs on wild bulls. Animals (wild bull, dog, fox, wild boar, goat with twisted horns, gazelle, mountain goat, insects, etc.), various

objects (bows, spears, sickles), people in masks are depicted in a unique way

11. The Plane Syrob

The Syrob maple is a revered "tree of life", a thousand years old. The tree trunk is hollow, and the hollow formed in it is so large that there used to be a small school

inside, which could fit twenty students with a teacher. Now there is a mini-museum inside. The sycamore tree is protected as a natural monument and is a local shrine.

12. The Cave Of Teshik-Tash

The Teshik-Tash cave-grotto is located in the Baysuntau mountains and is famous for the site of the Mousterian culture and the burial of a Neanderthal girl found there. The horns of a mountain goat were placed around the ritual burial and a circle of red

paint was drawn. In addition, about 3,000 tools were found in the cave. The cave itself is located at an altitude of 1550 meters above sea level. Climbing to the top of the mountain, you can see the Karshi steppe and

the main road leading to the village of Derbent.

13. Omonkhona Health Resort

To the east of the center of Baysun district, a sign on the side of the main highway will lead you to the Omonkhona sanatorium. The sanatorium is located in the village of Omonkhona. According to local elders, people have lived here for 700 years. This is evidenced by the old cemetery in the village and the tombstones located on it. The word "Omon" means healthy, safe, peaceful, serene, and the word "hona" means room, place, address, space. Thus, "Omonkhona" is a place of peace, health and peacefulness. Turning off the main road, you will reach the

center of the village, walking 15 kilometers through the hills.

14. Khoja Gur Gur Ota Array

The Khoja Gur Gur Ota array is one of the most striking sights of the Baysun mountains, an unusual giant peak with a five – hundred-meter cliff on one side and deep canyons on the other. "Father of all caves" – this is the name of the mountain range Khoja Gur Gur Ota. This place attracts not only mountaineers and extreme athletes. There is an ancient shrine and a gorge with a holy spring.

15. Topalang reservoir

There are 5 reservoirs in the Surkhandarya region, one of which is the Topalang reservoir. Its construction began in 1982 in the Sariosyo district. Today, the height of the dam is 122 meters and it is one of the most attractive places of the Surkhandarya oasis, rich in natural diversity. The main

water source of the reservoir is the Topalang river, which is formed by a tributary of the Karatag and Topalang rivers flowing from the southern Hissar mountain ranges, and is a right tributary of the Amu Darya. Topalang means "Red river" in Tajik. The river is 175 km long and the basin area is 13,500 km. From June to August, the river floods.

16. Sangardak Waterfall

Sangardak waterfall is located 205 kilometers from the city of Termez, on the territory of the Sariosyo district. Sangardak can rightly be called one of the most beautiful places in Uzbekistan. Water falling from a height breaks into billions of microscopic splashes that rise into the air in

the form of a substance similar to fog. The rocks surrounding the waterfall are covered with green moss. According to local tradition, if you tie a small piece of cloth on the territory of Sangardak and make a wish, it will certainly come true.

17. Hojaipok Hospital

Hojaipok is the hospital and a place of pilgrimage in same time. Name Hojaipok - the nickname of Hazrat Abdurahmon Ibn Andes. This cave is located at the foot of mount Kenagi. The depth of the cave has not been fully studied by experts. Healing spring water that flows from the surface of the cave, has a length of 45 meters and goes

into a small underground river. About 200 liters of water come out of the cave per second. The composition of the water was studied by the laboratory of the research center of Semashko, it contains sodium, potassium, calcium, sodium bicarbonate, silicic acid, nitrogen, iron, aluminum and other trace elements.

18. The Settlement of Dalvarzintepa

Among the monuments of the Kushan Empire (I-IV centuries AD), a special place is occupied by the ancient settlement of Dalvarzintepa, which is located in the Shurchi district, 60 km from Termez. During the excavations, various ivory items,

precious stones, coins, and fine ceramics dating back to the Greco-Bactrian era were found in the settlement. A special place is occupied by the world's oldest chess pieces (I-II centuries AD).

19. The Bridge of Alexander

The ancient bridge was built in the XVI century and is located on the site of an ancient trade road that connected the southern regions of the Hissar mountains with old Termez. Now the bridge is located near the M 41 highway in the territory of the Kumkurgan district. The locals call it "the

bridge Gisht-Kuprik" or "bridge of Iskander Zulkarnain". Local legend says that this place was crossed by Alexander the Great with his army. Initially, the bridge served as an aqueduct and a stream 20 meters wide and 10 meters deep passed under it.

20. Jarkurgan minaret

The minaret is located in the village of Minor, located between Kumkurgan and Termez. It was built in 1109 by order of Sultan Sanjar. Now its height is more than twenty meters, but at the time of construction it reached forty-three. Looking at the tower, it is impossible to take your eyes off the decoration. Skilfully executed masonry "herringbone" creates the effect of weaving. And when you stand under the minaret, you get the impression that the masonry is not brick at all, but fabric. The tower consists of sixteen semi-columns that are attached to each other.

Surkhandarya region is rich in not only historical monuments but also the most beautiful scenarios, magnificent places that worth to see in life.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth noting that there are enough opportunities in the region to increase the potential of tourism and other tourism types. This requires a number of measures to increase the number of new high-quality ecotourism facilities, thus stimulating the country's economy.

For example, it is possible to increase the number of jobs by developing and increasing the number of marketing research organizations in the tourism system, advertising historical monuments and relics, finding and creating new sites for ecotourism, increasing and improving additional types of services related to tourism: household services, communications, transport, etc. Also, it is worth noting that paying great attention to the development of the situation in the

tourist market when setting prices is the right choice of service personnel.

On this basis, Surkhandarya region will have to implement joint investment projects with Japan, Austria, Afghanistan and Tajikistan - the priority areas for cooperation. It is also

necessary to establish cooperation with Turkey, Pakistan and India, as well as China, Thailand and South Korea, based on the region's potential for pilgrimage and Buddhist tourism.

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